

move up the rice foliage. They enter folded leaves and prey on larvae, carrying them between their mandibles back to the tunnels. One *Diacamma* sp. worker (see photo) was observed to transport 4–10 larvae/hour; its greatest activity is from 0900 to 1030 and from 1600 to

1730 hours. Six ant species – *Camponotus* nr. *devestivus* Wheeler, *C.* nr. *nawai* Ito, *Diacamma* sp., *Odontomachus* sp., *Odontoponera transversa* (F. Smith), and *Solenopsis germinata* (F.) (identified by Dr. R. Sonobe, Japan) – were found to prey on

the leaf folder larvae, but *Diacamma* was the most abundant. Because of its greater prevalence, that species appears to be a better predator of the leaf folder than the carabid beetle *Chlaenius* sp. that we found during the 1977 season.

Pest management and control WEEDS

The black beetle: an efficient weed feeder in Bangladesh

Shamsul Alam and A.N.M. Rezaul Karim, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute (BRRI), Joydebpur, Dacca, Bangladesh

A black beetle *Haltica foveicollis* (Jac) (Chrysomelidae: Coleoptera) has been observed since 1969 to be a voracious feeder of the weed *Ludwigia octovalvis* (Jacq.) Raven in rice fields at the BRRI farm, Joydebpur. The insect was recently found to feed extensively on

another unidentified broadleaf weed of wheat and lentil fields. The beetle's grubs and adults nibble on the weed leaves and stunt the growth of the weeds so they cannot compete with the crops. In wheat and lentil fields at Madhabdi, many beetle grubs eat the weed leaves without damaging the crops. The beetle virtually controlled the weeds in the lentil fields.

The adult beetles are shiny bluish-black, 4.5 to 6 mm long, and about 3 mm wide. They are found in nonirrigated and in dryland fields. Peak beetle

populations have been observed in February–March, June–July, and October–November. The adult beetles are phototropic. More than 700 beetles/night have been caught in light traps at Joydebpur during the third week of February.

Some insects are known as important biological agents in the control of certain weeds. Considering its abundance and feeding habit, the black beetle *H. foveicollis* appears to be a potential control agent of the weeds mentioned.

Effect of weed management and water regime on the yield of farmers' bora rice

Nizam Uddin Ahmed, senior scientific officer; M. Zahidul Hoque, head; Akhter Hossain Khan, scientific officer; Rice Cropping Systems Division, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Dacca; and Shah Ahmed Ali Khan, extension officer, DND project, BWDB, Dacca, Bangladesh

Because the intensity of weed problems depends on the agroecological situation, the control measures vary from place to place. To compare the farmers' weed control practices with the unweeded check and other research-managed weeding treatments superimposed in farmers' fields, trials were conducted with transplanted boro rice in several farmers' fields at two test sites in Bangladesh. At Salna, Joydebpur, Dacca, there was little or no standing water most of the time during crop growth because the fields were not regularly irrigated. At Shimrail in Dacca-Narayanganj-Demra (DND) irrigation project of BWDB, the fields had 5–10 cm standing water almost all the time during crop growth.

Average grain yield of boro rice as affected by water regime and weed control practices at 2 test sites, 1979–80 boro season, Dacca, Bangladesh.

Weed control practice ^a	Salna ^b		DND ^c	
	Grain yield (t/ha) of Pajam	Change in yield from unweeded check (%)	Grain yield (t/ha) of BR3	Change in yield from unweeded check (%)
Unweeded check	2.78	100	3.75	100
Weeded once 3 WT	3.22	116	3.95	105
Weeded twice, 3 and 5 WT	3.89	140	4.01	107
Weed free	4.38	158	3.87	103
Farmers' weeding practice	3.14	113	3.81	102

^aWT = weeks after transplanting. Farmers' weeding practice = 2 weedings: 4 and 6 WT at Salna; 4 and 7 WT at DND. ^bAv of 4 replications in 2 fields having little or no standing water during crop growth. ^cAv of 3 replications in 3 fields having 5 to 10 cm standing water during crop growth.

Except for the weeding operations in the superimposed treatments, farmers did all field operations including weeding in their respective fields. Crop-cuts were made in both the research-managed and farmer-managed plots and grain yields were adjusted at 14% moisture content.

Results indicate (see table) that with inadequate water management at Salna, farmers achieved a 13% yield increase over the control by weeding twice (4 and 6 weeks after transplanting [WT]); but by keeping the fields weed free, they could achieve a 58% yield increase. At

DND with better water management, the grain yield from the unweeded plot was reasonably good and farmers' weeding did not cause much increase in yield. Maximum yield increase (7%) over the control was obtained by weeding twice – 3 and 5 WT. The data from the two sites indicate that proper water management during crop growth can considerably reduce the weeding requirements in rice fields. It was also noted that in cases of short water supply, better weed management is required for maximum rice yields. ■